

SOCIAL INCLUSION OF PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES IN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

The contemporary world, the job market is constantly changing due to the inclusion of new technologies and forms of organization of the production process, which requires the worker to develop skills that enable his permanence in employment in the face of such a competitive scenario. In the case of a worker with a disability, remaining in the job market is even more difficult due to several factors, whether social, economic or even cultural. The paper is related to an exploratory research related to bibliography concerning the contribution of a support based on constructive theory in the area of public health when there is a perception of the physically disabled at all levels. It is concluded that in Brazil there are still huge and old problems that demand immediate solutions and that over the years go unnoticed in society as if they were not important. When people with disabilities actually want to circulate and participate in public spaces, despite the legislation in their favor, their rights are denied, which is something unacceptable in a society that claims to be democratic and inclusive.

Keywords: Inclusion, disability, public health, Inclusive

1 INTRODUCTION

This article is part of the Inclusive Education line and brings this scenario to reality, seeking solutions for better applicability of this teaching. Inclusion in school refers to everyone's right to education, and for people who are the target audience of special education (people with disabilities, global developmental disorders or high abilities/giftedness), several adaptations and adaptations are necessary. of materials, physical and architectural structure, resources and differentiated pedagogical support to facilitate your educational process.

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Disability has always been present in human life, whether transitory or permanent; discovering the meaning of their existence and overcoming this difference is a challenge. People with disabilities have been seen and treated in different ways throughout history.

The problem presented aims to search for equal treatment between men is tireless. Society is inclined in continuous movements to achieve the long-awaited equality. And it is discussed all the time: "What is equality?". What is being equal? Firstly, with regard to the term "special needs" used as a synonym for "disabilities" (SASSAKI, 1997, p. 15) both in academia and in people's daily lives to supposedly mitigate the value of the latter term, Sasaki (1997) explains that use is inappropriate, since special needs cover other atypical conditions, in addition to those resulting from disabilities, such as psychological, emotional, mental, learning, organic and behavioral disorders, in addition to social situations that lead to marginalization. of people.

This article aims to study social inclusion with disabilities, in search of their fundamental rights as a human person. and specifically, to contextualize the Brazilian policy proposals for the education of people with disabilities and identify the bases on which they are sustained; ensure that the State treats its citizens as equals, even with differences that are perceptible to the naked eye and represent the right to work as a means of forming citizenship.

The methodology seeks to deepen the bibliographic research and the literature base will seek knowledge through material found in scientific articles, theses and books published on platforms available on the internet and field research. Thus, the research is mainly based on studies of scientific articles, journals and reliable electronic media, and a literature review is also carried out.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Concepts and Classification

According to SILVA (2009), the concept of disability encompasses a medical model, in which it is understood as a limitation of the individual, in relation to a social model, which

understands disability as a result of limitations and body structures, but also of the influence of factors of the society of the environment in which it is inserted. The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health is used as a tool, within the scope of biopsychosocial assessment.

The concepts of “disability” and “people with disabilities” have undergone major transformations over the decades. As societies change their view of the disabled, new paradigms and denominations are being developed. The literature does not present a specific definition of disability, just as there is no consensus on what a person with a disability is.

In health, education and even in the evaluation criteria for receiving government benefits, there are different definitions of disability. As a general rule, disability presupposes the existence of variations in some skills that qualify as restrictions or injuries. What does not exist, however, is a consensus on which variations in skills and functionalities would characterize disabilities. (BAMPI; GUILHEM; ALVES, 2010, p. 3).

The World Health Organization (WHO) understands the term “disability as a difference in the structural, psychological and physiological organization of the organism. Disability as the functional consequence of disability, so that daily tasks are not performed. (BRAZIL, 1993:20).

In Brazil, the 1988 Constitution was the starting point for the inclusion of this group in the most diverse social scenarios, including the world of work. According to the Magna Carta, work is a social right, and any discrimination in terms of admission criteria for workers with disabilities is prohibited.

2.2 Discrimination and the Disabled

Firstly, with regard to the term “special needs” used as a synonym for “disabilities” (SASSAKI, 1997, p. 15) both in the academic environment and in people's daily lives as a way of supposedly attenuating the value of this last term, Sasaki (1997) explains that use is inappropriate, since special needs cover other atypical conditions, in addition to those resulting from disabilities, such as psychological, emotional, mental, learning, organic and behavioral disorders, in addition to social situations that lead to marginalization. of people.

The use of the expression “special needs” as a modulator of the term “disability” is, for Diniz (2012, p. 10), a form of “discriminatory euphemism”. Also in a reflection on the use of “special needs”, it was detected by Irigaray (2011), in a study on the perception of external and internal publics regarding the policy.

The use of the euphemism “people with special needs”, recurrent in all the speeches of the non-disabled interviewees, reveals the intention to decorate with a kind of artistic curtain the stigma to which the minority in question is submitted. More than that, this language function plays the role of attenuator in the discourse, whose social purpose is to maintain a minimum of harmony between the interactants, masking eventual political or social conflicts and, at the same time, giving the sender the aura of “politically speaking”. correct". (IRIGARAY; VERGARA, 2011, p. 1090)

That said, we argue that the semantic attempts to avoid the use of the term “disability”, in addition to bringing imprecision to what is intended to be addressed, would be an attempt to veil the stigma and discrimination suffered by PwD. However, our understanding is that it is precisely necessary to give visibility and discuss the treatment given to PwD in society and, more specifically, in the job market, in order to improve discussions on diversity.

This time, according to Sassaki (2005), with which we agree, the term “person with a disability” would be appropriate, as it brings value to the person and is marked by empowerment and responsibility to contribute to an inclusive society, contrary to terms used until the early 1980s, such as “exceptional”, “handicapped”, “defective”, “disabled” and “invalid”, or others such as “lame”, “crippled” and “retarded”, which were detected, at the beginning of disability studies, as being marked by violence (DINIZ, 2012).

In addition, the term “person with a disability” is different from the meaning of “people with disabilities” or “people with special needs”, given that “a person only carries something that he or she may not carry, deliberately or casually.” (SASSAKI, 2005, p. 15).

According to Girondi and Santos (2011), in the current political, economic and social conjuncture, it appears that the condition of incapacity and disability is highlighted in the public health scenario, although it can be seen that assistance to this population is marginally inserted in the health system. Issues related to assistance to people with disabilities in Brazil still present a fragile, disjointed and discontinuous profile of actions both in the public and private spheres.

2.3 Legislation for the Disabled in Education and Work

National legislation has sought to offer students with disabilities the possibility of continuing their academic and professional lives. The Law of Directives and Bases of National Education (LDB) n° 9394/96 points towards the access of the student with special educational needs to the regular school and dedicates Chapter V to Special Education, ratifying it as a constitutional duty in three articles (articles 58, 59 and 60).

In article 59, item II, this Law recommends that education systems must ensure the “[. . .] specific terminality for those who cannot reach the level required for completing elementary school, due to their deficiencies, and acceleration to complete the school program for the gifted in a shorter time” (BRASIL, 1996, p. 37). In this sense, several laws were created to protect workers with disabilities, including the Quota Law, which obliges companies that have more than 100 workers to reserve a percentage of vacancies for the disabled. Even with the regulation of these laws, the 2010 IBGE Census shows that, of the more than 190 million people in Brazil, more than 45 million Brazilians (24% of the population) have some type of disability. Companies that hire people with disabilities will be obliged to train new employees, given little or no professional experience, which generates special attention from their employers.

Brazil closes its eyes when it comes to guaranteeing these people satisfactory professional training opportunities, since it is a matter of public order to include them in schools that are trained and adapted for the most diverse types of disabilities, and there is an absence of public policies for quality focused on this issue.

However, there is a difficulty for companies in hiring people with disabilities, due to prejudice and lack of knowledge about the disability.

2.4 The Social Ideology

The ideological content of the principle of isonomy lies precisely in the inexistence of guarantees or disadvantages, in the equitable treatment given to all citizens. In the Brazilian Federal Constitution, it is found in article 5, item II.

Faced with these considerations, they establish that the right to work represents a means of forming citizenship. Analyzing the coherence between the legal purpose of schooling for people with disabilities and the meanings attributed by the family to this schooling in the common class of regular schools and the role of private institutions in society should be to provide work. But, before that, there is a need for the State to guarantee the delivery of minimum social benefits for their effectiveness.

Aim to develop this work considering the links between educational policies and proposals for the area of Special Education. Seeking in them to apprehend the constitutive elements of the legislation for this area and in specific, for the schooling of the student with intellectual disability in the regular class of the regular school.

Considering that the certification of elementary school education for people with intellectual disabilities through specific terminality has been provided for in Law since 1996 and until the present moment what is observed is the uncertainty about it.

2.5 The Bottlenecks of Disability

In order to understand the bottlenecks they experience and the difficulties that people with disabilities need, we are reminded of the necessary form of increased attention to this clientele, and, in addition, a reformulation of the issues that involve the health of the professional of the worker with a disability, limitations and occupational risks that people with disabilities have, who develop their work actions in university, veterinary and dental hospitals.

Regarding the issue of people with disabilities, there was a predominance of the essentially biological model of care, in which it was possible to perceive that only acute conditions, which are short-term and manifest in an unpredictable way, were considered. Due to this nature, the aforementioned model has become insufficient, fragmented and lacking in answers. In the current political, economic and social conjuncture, it appears that the condition of incapacity and disability is highlighted in the public health scenario, although it can be noticed that the assistance to this population is marginally inserted in the health system. Issues related to assistance to people with disabilities in Brazil still present a fragile, disjointed and discontinuous profile of actions both in the public and private spheres (GIRONDI; SANTOS, 2011).

2.6 Some Type of Disability in the Population

Data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) reveal that 6.2% of the Brazilian population has some type of disability. The National Health Survey (PNS) considered four types of disabilities: hearing, visual, physical and intellectual. The survey was released today (21) by the IBGE and carried out in partnership with the Ministry of Health.

Among the types of disability surveyed, visual impairment is the most representative and affects 3.6% of Brazilians, being more common among people over 60 years old (11.5%). The intense or very intense degree of limitation makes it impossible for 16% of the visually impaired to perform usual activities such as going to school, working and playing.

Also according to the IBGE, 0.8% of the Brazilian population has some type of intellectual disability, and the majority (0.5%) was born with limitations. Of the total number

of people with intellectual disabilities, more than half (54.8%) have an intense or very intense degree of limitation and about 30% attend some health rehabilitation service.

People with hearing impairment represent 1.1% of the Brazilian population, and this type of disability was the only one that presented statistically different results by color or race, being more common in white people (1.4%), than in black people (0.9%). About 0.9% of Brazilians became deaf as a result of illness or accident and 0.2% were born deaf. Of the total number of hearing impaired, 21% have an intense or very intense degree of limitations, which compromises their usual activities.

2.7 Social Mobilization of PCD Law

In Brazil, the first speeches in relation to the rights of PwD took place in the mid-1960s; in relation to social mobilization. (FRANCE, 2009:25).

The 1988 Constitution was the starting point for the inclusion of this group in the most diverse social scenarios, including the world of work. According to the Magna Carta, work is a social right, and any discrimination in terms of admission criteria for workers with disabilities is prohibited.

In this sense, several laws were created to protect workers with disabilities, including the Quota Law, which obliges companies that have more than 100 workers to reserve a percentage of vacancies for the disabled. Even with the regulation of these laws, the 2010 IBGE Census shows that, of the more than 190 million people in Brazil, more than 45 million Brazilians (24% of the population) have some type of disability. Companies that hire people with disabilities will be obliged to train new employees, given little or no professional experience, which generates special attention from their employers.

This mobilization helps the state to discuss the rights of people with disabilities. Today, according to the Ministry of Health (2009:43), the right that supports people with disabilities is considered in the Federal Constitution of 1988 (FRANÇA, 2008:27).

Ordinance No. 10.060/2002 (National Health Policy for Persons with Disabilities covers the details for actions both in the Unified Health System – SUS and in the various governmental and non-governmental instances.

In recent decades, the issue of disability has been gaining more and more space in the social sphere, where people with some type of disability are seen as a group no longer as isolated cases that deserve attention by the State and society. “The issue of disability should not be an exclusive matter of biomedical knowledge, but mainly of political actions and State

interventions. These two goals paved the way for a new look at disability” (DINIZ, 2012, p. 19).

Brazil closes its eyes when it comes to guaranteeing these people satisfactory professional training opportunities, since it is a matter of public order to include them in schools that are trained and adapted for the most diverse types of disabilities, and there is an absence of public policies for quality focused on this issue.

Before the Federal Constitution of 1988, people with disabilities were assisted by charity, welfare actions were the only means of subsistence for this part of the population and with it Social Assistance, which together with Social Security and Health, form the tripod of Social Security.

3 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The article seeks to show that the relevance of the issue of disability in the service is even more latent. This is because the treatment of disability still seems to be motivated by legal impositions and not by the existence of an inclusive culture in the Institution, similar to what happens in private companies.

There are still stigmas and prejudices that should be non-existent, given that personal, social and economic well-being is a right of people with disabilities and must be guaranteed by the Government and its bodies.

Thinking about the articulation between School Education and Inclusion refers to the consideration of different obstacles, among which, the adoption of a more socially committed professional action as a central element in the educational process, because only from this articulation, the different and complex representations that permeate the process of school inclusion of students with special needs can be approached from a consistent theoretical perspective, which supports new areas of intelligibility in understanding human development and inclusive school relationships.

School issues are shown to be controversial in the same intensity that the problems arising, incidents or related to school institutions are shown to be complex. And this is the challenge to be overcome, a political and ideological formation, added to a critical professional practice that builds the Brazilian reality, with a commitment to understanding human diversity for the development of a more democratic society.

It is necessary for educational institutions to make the study environments of students with disabilities as adapted as possible, providing pleasant study moments and ensuring that

this student with disabilities is not separated from the others, promoting a favorable coexistence, this environment will be strengthened through of non-formal spaces.

In this context, understanding the difficulties that regular education teachers face in the school environment is to practice empathy, perceive complaints and difficulties in teaching and learning, lack of preparation and even specialized training, based on this understanding, reminds us of the need for a redoubled attention to this part of society and, in addition, a reformulation of the issues that involve teaching and inclusive education, in public and private institutions, are presented in a synthesized way. In addition, the analysis of current national and institutional legislation describes that the norms that deal with work for people with disabilities have incorporated the conceptual change of disability, which went from the medical model to the social model (DINIZ; BARBOSA; SANTOS, 2009; DINIZ, 2012).

As for normative acts, especially from the mid-2000s, they acquired a transformational character, proposing changes to eliminate prejudice and discrimination and to include PwD in the labor market, through the elimination of barriers accessibility, providing conditions for qualification and professional training and access to positions and jobs of their free choice and aptitude.

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